

Federated Learning for Reliability Modeling of Distribution Cable Networks: A Danish Case Study

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Abstract—Medium-voltage (MV) cable networks are the backbone of electricity distribution. However, in Denmark, increasing age-related failure rates of older paper-insulated lead-covered (PILC) cables raise concerns and call for modernizing the cable infrastructure. The increased need for investment and maintenance activities requires sophisticated tools to improve decision-making. In this context, Machine Learning (ML) has the potential to transform the industry, provide timely predictions, improve resource allocation, and ensure reliable grid operation. Unfortunately, MV cable failures are rare events and thus, in combination with data quality issues, challenge the development of effective ML model development. Federated learning (FL) offers a privacy-preserving, collaborative approach, enabling distribution system operators (DSOs) to share insights without jeopardizing data privacy. Consequently, this paper explores the potential of FL frameworks for MV cable reliability prediction, leveraging federated ML models like Random Survival Forests. A case study using publicly available survival data investigates key factors that affect the applicability of federated learning in cable networks. The results illustrate the viability of FL for fostering collaborative data-driven maintenance strategies, particularly for DSOs with limited data.

Index Terms—Distribution Grids, Medium Voltage Cables, Federated Learning, Predictive Maintenance, Federated Survival Forest, Denmark, Asset Management

I. INTRODUCTION

In many countries in Europe and worldwide, the distribution grid is managed not by a single DSO but by many, each varying significantly in size, data accessibility, and operational conditions. Despite their differences, DSOs face common challenges, including the urgent need to modernize and invest in distribution grid infrastructure. The growing demand for investment and modernization in power distribution systems necessitates strong data-centric tools, e.g., based on machine learning (ML) techniques, to aid decision-making and improve maintenance strategies. Medium-voltage (MV) cable networks are a key focus for data-driven reliability studies because of their unique characteristics. They often consist of older components, are less accessible than high-voltage networks, and notably contribute to grid outages.

However, ML-based reliability prediction of MV cables faces substantial challenges. For example, the distributed nature of datasets complicates data combination, and data limitations significantly hinder appropriate modeling [1], resulting in overfitting risks and reduced generalizability [2]. In

this context, centralized and collaborative model development has the potential to significantly improve the performance of models assessing the reliability of MV cable networks, particularly benefiting DSOs with data scarcity during failure reporting.

However, such collaborative model development introduces several challenges. It requires the central collection and sharing of data among the stakeholders involved. However, data owners, mainly DSOs, are not always capable or willing to share their data due to privacy and security concerns or further business interests. In addition, distribution grid data is often classified as critical infrastructure, and many models might involve data from smart meters, which are protected under the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and require stringent privacy safeguards. As a result, depending on the targeted feature set, collaborative model development could lead to serious data privacy concerns.

Moreover, developing a centralized model also requires centralized data collection and management. This calls for a robust infrastructure that facilitates efficient data sharing among stakeholders and a central authority overseeing the process. Various technical solutions have been proposed to facilitate central data access. For instance, as one possibility, [2] suggests a decentralized Entity relational (ER) data model for data storage and management to facilitate data sharing and access for distributed data in the context of reliability modeling of MV cables.

However, these approaches necessitate additional look-up services and confidentiality agreements, which might result in further data collection and management costs. Moreover, security concerns might persist in scenarios involving highly sensitive data.

Implementing a privacy-preserving and distributed learning method, such as federated learning [3], can mitigate the concerns above. It allows for the collaborative improvement of reliability models without sharing raw data, but instead, the model parameters. Federated learning leverages decentralized datasets to aggregate diverse insights from DSOs and MV cable networks. Consequently, it can help improve the reliability prediction performance of MV cables without collecting the data centrally. This could address the DSOs' data-sharing concerns and yield a more robust and performant model.

Consequently, this paper explores the application of federated learning methods in the context of reliability prediction of MV cables. It begins by providing an overview of previous studies and frameworks that leverage federated learning within electricity distribution, particularly in asset management and component reliability analysis. The study then narrows down to MV cable networks by reflecting on design considerations and influence factors specific to the reliability assessment of cable networks. The paper proceeds by implementing a selection of the modeling choices presented, utilizing a publicly available survival dataset. This allows for identifying potential implementation opportunities and barriers, emphasizing federated learning as a viable option for fostering more collaborative and data-driven predictive maintenance of MV cables.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A recent literature review focusing on advancing power system services with privacy-preserving federated learning [4] emphasizes that the main driving factors for implementing federated learning are privacy and security concerns. However, the authors in [4] list also further reasons to apply federated learning in power systems, such as communication overhead costs, data insufficiency, and heterogeneity. All are also applicable and relevant to the reliability prediction of MV cables. Besides reviewing the potential of federated learning on a higher level, previous studies also identified federated learning as a promising application field for collaborative asset management. In the context of asset management of distribution grid components, federated learning has already been applied to different components and problems such as the diagnosis of PD in gas-insulated switchgear [5], [6], the diagnosis of insulation defects in gas-insulated switchgear [7], for power transformer fault diagnosis [8] and voltage control [9].

Additionally, [4] shows that several federated techniques have been integrated into numerous ML methods, such as supervised, unsupervised, and reinforcement learning. Furthermore, there are also more specific techniques that propose the integration of federated learning for survival analysis. Examples are the Federated Survival Forest (FSF) [10] and the Federated Cox Proportional Hazards Model [11]. But also for more advanced ML models, federated techniques and frameworks have been proposed, such as for graph neural networks [12].

Despite the availability of examples from distribution grid asset management and different methods, to the best of the author's knowledge, federated learning has not been applied to reliability studies targeting cable networks. Consequently, there is a research gap regarding whether the concept of federated learning also applies to cable reliability modeling. Furthermore, it is to be elaborated to what extent and under which circumstances DSOs can profit from a federated learning concept in cable reliability modeling.

This paper aims to address the aforementioned research gap by reflecting on influencing factors and design considerations

of federated learning frameworks specific to the reliability modeling of MV cables. Additionally, it underlines the reflections by implementing a characteristic federated learning framework, based on a publicly available survival dataset describing the survival time of crowdfunding projects [13].

III. DESIGN CONSIDERATIONS AND INFLUENCING FACTORS

Many factors can impact the design of and, therewith, also, the benefit of a federated learning framework, such as the number and size of clients, data quality, and the number of shared features. Table I illustrates the various elements influencing the design of a federated learning framework, specifically focusing on reliability modeling of MV cables. Critical factors include the number of participating DSOs, the availability of shared features, and the selected aggregation technique. All are briefly further elaborated below.

Number of clients: The implementation of a federated learning framework is only relevant if a substantial amount of clients participate in the decentralized model training. In the context of reliability modeling of MV cable networks, the number of clients equals the number of DSOs willing to participate in collaborative model development. In Denmark, there are 36 DSOs. However, the number might be higher in other countries in Europe and globally. In theory, also, cross-country model training is feasible. Consequently, a realistic range for the number of clients specified for a federated learning framework for reliability modeling of MV cables ranges from 3 to 50.

Data Size: Another factor that influences the relevance of federated learning is the dataset size. In the context of reliability prediction of medium voltage cable networks, the data size needs to be differentiated into the number of cable instances to be investigated and the number of failure records. The number of cable instances is typically very high, particularly if models target most granular data, such as the medium voltage cable sections. However, cable failures are rare events. Furthermore, as discussed in [14], after combination with other datasets such as asset registers, the number of failure information usable for model training might be drastically reduced, leading to relatively small data sizes of failure records, sometimes only around a hundred failure reports for smaller DSOs. Very generally speaking, these data scarcity challenges might favor federated learning. By aggregating insights from local models, federated approaches might overcome individual data limitations and facilitate collaboration among otherwise isolated DSOs.

Data distribution: Another impact driver for the federated learning framework is how the data is distributed. In theory, equally distributed data across different clients would reduce the applicability of federated learning frameworks, as data sharing and collaborative modeling would not provide additional insights. However, distribution grids and cable networks span a large geographical area. Further, failure and aging dynamics are multifold. Consequently, failures and cable parameters are expected to be distributed unequally across the

TABLE I
DESIGN CONSIDERATIONS AND INFLUENCING FACTORS FOR FEDERATED LEARNING IN RELIABILITY MODELING OF MV CABLES

Parameter	Description	Example
Number of Clients	The total number of participating DSOs in the federated model development. Even though there is no technical limit, practical considerations might range between 3-50 individual companies.	3-50 DSOs
Data Size (Cable Instances)	The volume of cable instances available for training at each DSO. The number of instances will differ depending on the level of data granularity selected, e.g., the selection of cable sections, systems, or radials.	20.000 - 100.000 cable instances
Data Size (Failure Instances)	The volume of failure instances available for training at each DSO. The number might differ depending on the combination and enrichment techniques applied as well as depending on the reliability method selected.	200 - 10.000 failure instances
Data Distribution	An important factor influencing the performance of federated learning frameworks is how the data is distributed across clients.	Non-Independent and Identically Distributed
Number of Features	The dimensionality of the dataset used for training the model.	10-100 features
Reliability Modeling Method	The method used to model the reliability of medium voltage cables has an impact on the averaging strategy of designing the federated learning framework.	e.g., ML-based Survival Models
Aggregation Strategy	The method used to combine client updates into a global model.	e.g., Weighted Averaging

network and across companies, which favors the application of federated learning techniques. However, future work needs to quantify this general observation and provide measures of how the data distributions vary across different DSOs.

Number of common features: A key consideration in designing federated learning frameworks is the availability of features that can be used for collaborative training across all clients. After evaluating the dataset for Denmark, this paper defines the practical range of common features between 10 and 100 at most. This approach assumes that data standardization has been achieved and a unified data model is implemented. However, features should only be added if they provide additional insights into the model performance and do not favor the risk of overfitting. Furthermore, there are approaches that do not strictly require the same features across different clients [15], yet such approaches will not be further examined within the context of this paper.

Reliability modeling method: Another factor to consider is that the federated learning framework should support the chosen method for reliability modeling. As discussed in Section II, many conventional and advanced ML models already support the integration of federated learning. However, as these come with specific requirements, one must decide if these requirements align with the constraints and objectives of the reliability modeling task. For instance, the federated learning framework must ensure compatibility with the reliability metrics chosen for the analysis. However, further dependencies between the selected reliability model and other framework elements, including the aggregation strategy, must also be considered.

Aggregating Strategy: In federated learning, the aggregation strategy specifies how local models from distributed DSOs are integrated into a global model. It is highly linked to the selected method during reliability modeling. For example, a tree-based model may require strategies to aggregate local trees into a global structure, such as merging or pruning. In contrast, aggregation for deep learning models typically involves combining neural network weights or gradients. For

this, a common approach is FedAvg, in which the local model parameters are weighted and averaged based on the dso's dataset size. This approach ensures that DSO with larger datasets have a proportionately greater influence on the global model. While applicable in many cases, for predicting the reliability of MV cables, variations in data distribution, like imbalanced failure records among DSOs, may require different aggregation strategies.

IV. CASE STUDY

This chapter aims to strengthen the reflections collected in the previous chapter by selecting a subset of the formulated federated learning framework parameters and employing them on a publicly available survival data set [13].

It indicates what a possible implementation of a federated learning setup for ML-based reliability modeling could look like. Furthermore, it emphasizes how variations in the described framework parameters can affect performance. This might support future work and help DSOs identify conditions where federated learning proves particularly useful. Furthermore, it recognizes the practical constraints and narrows the discussion down to concentrating on realistic federated learning framework configurations.

Using a publicly available dataset for this evaluation comes with several advantages. First, it strengthens the reproducibility of the experiments. Secondly, it ensures that the underlying data is representative to provide robust and accurate model performance. Unfortunately, the later can not be fully ensured for the data collected in this case study.

The data is synthetically divided into different clients to model different federated scenarios. Moreover, different functions are implemented to enable different data splits. This enables customization of the number of DSOs, modeling of the data size, and distribution of cable failures during both the training and testing phases.

As the model of choice for the reliability modeling, this study selects the Random Survival Forest [16]. This approach is transformed into a federated design following [10], which is

also known as the FSF. Consequently, selecting this technique also narrows down the selection of the aggregation technique. As FSF is a tree-based model, aggregation is realized by combining the decision trees of the individual models. Again, multiple techniques of aggregating the trees are possible. This case study considers three options: a selection of all available trees from all clients, a selection of a random subset, and the weighted mean of the trees. However, the authors acknowledge that there are aggregation techniques available that are more targeted for implementation within a survival model, such as aggregating the trees based on the Integrated Brier Score of the models [10].

Another specialty of the FSF Model is that it allows for so-called "one-shot learning." In contrast to federated deep learning techniques, this does not require multiple communication rounds and iterative model updates between the DSO and central aggregation entity.

Eventually, the testing of different federated learning possibilities becomes possible. For example, as one option, Figure 1 visualizes the model results for 20 clients of equal size and stratified failure records. It is shown that, on average, the model performance among the clients increases due to federated learning. This contrast is even stronger for scenarios where the data sizes are not equally distributed, as Figure 2 highlights.

Figure 3 shows how dividing the dataset into more but smaller clients increases the average concordance gain across them. This emphasizes that the federated learning framework is particularly applicable for the reliability of medium voltage cables if multiple DSOs with either a smaller number of cables or failure records are involved.

Fig. 3. Average concordance gain over different hyperparameter runs - grouped after number of clients.

Similarly, Figure 4 emphasizes the impact of different data sizes. It is shown that the average concordance gain is significantly higher for scenarios where DSO datasets differ in size. One important thing to consider is the level of inequality. In this case study, the magnitude of data size inequality was specified manually. However, in practice, the severity of

the difference is defined by the DSO datasets. Consequently, future work must investigate how "unequally distributed" the data from different DSOs might be, before elaborating on the benefits of implementing a federated learning framework design.

Fig. 4. Average concordance gain over different hyperparameter runs - grouped after splitting strategy.

Different aggregation strategies indicated a limited impact on the average concordance gain within the defined case study. However, a slight tendency towards selecting all trees for the global model is observed. However, as it is expected that these insights might change for different hyperparameter selections, e.g., by increasing the number of trees per local and global model, future work must carefully iterate over the different aggregation techniques and verify the result of this case study.

Fig. 5. Average concordance gain over different hyperparameter runs - grouped after aggregation technique.

V. CONCLUSION

This study highlights the potential of federated learning to address the data privacy and collaboration challenges of data-driven reliability prediction for MV cable networks. By

Fig. 1. Federated Framework including 20 DSOs with equally distributed data sizes and failure data.

Fig. 2. Federated Framework including 20 DSOs with unequally distributed data sizes but same number of failure records.

leveraging decentralized datasets, federated learning can assist DSOs in improving predictive maintenance models collaboratively without compromising sensitive data. Although existing literature has outlined the benefits of collaborative reliability assessment for other distribution grid component types, such as transformers, studies targeting the specific characteristics of MV cable networks are lacking. This represents a significant research gap, particularly considering the broad range of applicable and available federated learning frameworks.

This paper implements different FSF model versions to demonstrate the implications of constructing a federated learning framework for the reliability modeling of MV cable networks. The analysis of various framework parameters, including number of clients involved and dataset size, reveals differences in model performance.

The findings underscore the relevance of employing federated learning for the stated issue. However, they also emphasize that a federated learning framework favors settings where many smaller DSOs with diverse data conditions are involved. In conclusion, this work underscores the importance of exploring real-world data distributions and advanced aggregation strategies to enhance the practical applicability of federated learning, establishing it as a viable solution for DSOs during reliability prediction of MV cable networks.

VI. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This manuscript has been developed within the framework of the InnoCYPES project, financially supported by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation

program, through the Marie Skłodowska Curie Grant agrmt. No 956433.

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